

ELUCIDATING INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL AND ITS IMPACT TO ENTREPRENEURSHIP STRATEGY AMONG MEDIUM-SIZED COMPANIES

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Elucidating Intellectual Capital and its Impact to Entrepreneurship Strategy among Medium-Sized Companies

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Abstract

In the evolving landscape of medium-sized enterprises, intellectual capital has been an essential component of entrepreneurship strategy. The purpose of this study is to determine the significant relationship between intellectual capital- comprising of structural, human and customer capital- and entrepreneurship strategy- in the aspects of creative capabilities, risk taking and entrepreneurial culture. The study is focused and limited only to medium-sized companies which provide a localized perspective as it employs a descriptive-correlational research design and a purposive sampling technique, intentionally selecting fifty employees from various medium-sized companies. Moreover, the data was gathered using a modified version of an existing questionnaire, which included sections on demographics, level of intellectual capital, and level of entrepreneurship strategy. The findings demonstrated that there is a high degree of intellectual capital in medium-sized companies. It was also discovered that there is a high level of entrepreneurship strategy in the same sector. Furthermore, the study discovered a substantial association between intellectual capital and the entrepreneurial approach of medium-sized businesses. This means that as intellectual capital increases, the entrepreneurship strategy tends also to increase.

Keywords: *intellectual capital, entrepreneurship strategy, medium-sized companies*

Introduction

Entrepreneurship strategy is a dynamic focal point of innovation and economic progress, as visionaries adeptly merge opportunities, resources, and measured risk-taking to shape the course of the future. Entrepreneurship, a driving force for economic growth, inherently involves risk (Chanda & Unel, 2021). Entrepreneurship strategy faces challenges in customer retention (Ascarza et al., 2018). Al Kurdi et al. (2023) further emphasized the ongoing challenges faced by organizations across diverse industries in attracting new customers and retaining existing ones. Consequently, various sectors experience contraction, suspension, or closure of their operations because of the loss of customers, leading to a significant reduction in their workforce (Alketbi, Alshurideh, & Al Kurdi, 2020).

In Nigeria, small and medium enterprise face challenges in fully implementing entrepreneurial strategies, notably due to limited credit availability from banks reluctant to provide financial support (Akhamiokhor & Adanikin, 2017). This stems from issues like inadequate documentation and poorly executed human resources strategies, contributing to a high failure rate of 70% within the first three years (Akingbolu, 2014). This difficulty is a result of SMEs' failure to effectively implement strategies, leading to the collapse and eventual demise of numerous businesses (Mwangi & Omhui, 2013).

Intellectual capital is a dynamic system of elements that produces knowledge and is fueled by knowledge evolving over time (Latilla, Frattini, Petruzzelli, & Berner, 2019). A study by Sales et al. (2016) claimed that many scientists argue that the underdevelopment of certain firms results from their failure to effectively harness intellectual capital for operational purposes, rather than being due to a shortage of financial resources. Furthermore, Sadq et al. (2020) drew a clear association between intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy. Several research investigations have underscored the pivotal importance of intellectual capital in influencing the strategies of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). These studies emphasize the imperative for entrepreneurs to adeptly harness their intellectual resources (Rexhepi, Ibrahim, & Veselic, 2013).

In the Philippines, entrepreneurs are faced with challenges in implementing effective entrepreneurship strategies, particularly in securing access to financial resources (Gozun & Rivera, 2021). In addition, the study of Aldaba (2012) emphasized that despite the crucial role of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in driving economic growth, creating employment, and fostering innovation, a significant number of them struggle to secure financing from various sources, impacting their ability to start, innovate, grow, and compete. In the same context, some studies highlight that limited access to financial resources is a common issue for SMEs, constraining their growth, competitive response, and business diversification (Ghosh, 2016).

While intellectual capital is widely acknowledged as a critical driver for innovation and competitive advantage, the definite ways in which medium-sized companies leverage their intellectual capital to develop and implement entrepreneurship strategies remain underexplored. This research aims to address this gap by examining the interplay between intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy specifically in the context of medium-sized enterprises. Further, the urgency to conduct the study is also emphasized by its potential benefits.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study is to determine the impact of intellectual capital on entrepreneurship strategy. Specifically, it sought to answer

the following queries:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of job classification and years of experience?
2. What is the level of intellectual capital in terms of structural capital, human capital and customer capital?
3. What is the level of entrepreneurship strategy in terms of creative capabilities, risk taking and entrepreneurial culture?
4. Is there a significant relationship between intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy?

Literature Review

Intellectual Capital

Intellectual capital serves as a non-monetary, non-physical resource that facilitates organizational development by extracting knowledge-based value (Ansari et al., 2016). This knowledge, held by employees, influences the development of business processes, databases, systems, and relationships. Previous studies have examined the impact of intellectual capital on organizational performance (Pedro et al., 2018). Also, prior research on intellectual resources has identified three major factors: intangible assets, capabilities for creating and modifying assets, and social relationships that underpin all knowledge developments (Gallagher, 2012).

In addition, a study by Sales et al. (2016) claimed that many scientists argue that the underdevelopment of certain firms results from their failure to effectively harness intellectual capital for operational purposes, rather than being due to a shortage of financial resources. Moreover, intellectual capital is widely acknowledged as a key element for enhancing an organization's assets, allowing it to gain a competitive edge in a dynamic market environment (Mutuc et al., 2019). Unfortunately, entrepreneurs often hold misconceptions about intellectual capital, highlighting the need for educational programs to rectify such misconceptions and promote effective intellectual capital management (Secundo et al., 2018).

Human Capital. A study by Massaro et al. (2015) emphasizes that the presence of a diverse range of skills, expertise, and knowledge within a company's workforce contributes to the generation of innovative ideas in organizational development. Leal-Rodriguez et al. (2015) further emphasized that companies must require creativity among employees to maintain their strategic position in a competitive environment. Yesil and Sozbilir (2013) said that companies should promote innovation among their workforce by providing them with suitable systems. Thus, Borjesson, Elmquist, and Hooge (2014) proposed that organizations should recognize the essential requirement for the continuous enhancement of individual innovation capabilities. Therefore, organizations can enhance their human capital by either attracting skilled individuals from outside the organization or by internally developing the skills of existing employees (Berezinets et al., 2016).

Structural Capital. Previous research has indicated that organizations with weak procedures and systems for monitoring their actions often struggle to achieve performance excellence (De Luca et al., 2020). Additionally, Borjesson, Elmquist, and Hooge (2014) emphasized the critical necessity of continuously enhancing individual innovation capability, engaging managers in the learning process, and enacting effective policies to optimize existing resources. Knowledge inherent in structural capital tends to accumulate and should be utilized in a recognized manner (Budiarti, 2017). However, Capron (2015) argues that businesses must constantly transform to stay pertinent, inventive, and competitive. Moreover, Dmitriev (2017) contends that a company's strategy should center around creating a framework for actively pursuing, adjusting to, and implementing innovations to secure a continuous influx of investments and competitive benefits.

Relational Capital/Customer Capital. Many manufacturing firms engage in close relationships with suppliers to leverage their skills, capabilities, and knowledge for developing innovative and cost-effective products at a rapid pace (Vătămănescu et al., 2019). Khadka and Maharjan (2017) states that in an effort to meet customer satisfaction, companies must be able to provide the best quality products. Moreover, Djumarno et al. (2018) demonstrated that better product quality will maintain high level of customer satisfaction, which encourages customers to make future purchases.

Entrepreneurship Strategy

Corporate entrepreneurship strategy (CES) aims to drive entrepreneurial efforts within firms across various industries (Kreiser et al., 2021). However, implementing these strategies often faces challenges, particularly in customer retention and acquisition, leading to declines in operations and workforce reductions (Al Kurdi et al., 2023; Ascarza, 2018). In Nigeria, SMEs struggle with CES due to limited credit access, poor documentation, and ineffective HR strategies, resulting in a high failure rate within the first three years (Akhamiokhor & Adanikin, 2017).

Consequently, several studies emphasize that restricted access to financial resources is a prevalent issue for SMEs, limiting their growth prospects, competitive responsiveness, and capacity for business diversification (Ghosh, 2016). The challenge stems from SMEs' ineffective implementation of strategies, leading to the collapse and ultimate demise of numerous businesses in Nigeria (Mwangi & Omhui, 2013). In the Philippines, SMEs encounter similar issues, particularly in securing financial resources, which hampers their ability to grow and compete (Gozun & Rivera, 2021).

Creative Capabilities. Creativity in entrepreneurship is both pre-cognitive and cognitive (Stammerjohan et al., 2019). Entrepreneurs often see creativity as separate from their business activities, despite its role in opportunity recognition and network building. Also,

Amabile (2017) highlighted that perceived work environments differentiate high- and low-creativity projects. Bilan et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of mastering science and technology for creativity and innovation. However, training employees maintain a skill level, including creative capabilities, incurs considerable costs, necessitating prudent resource allocation to align with desired goals (Saadouli, 2015). Moreover, Nasifoglu Elidemir et al. (2020) noted that fear-induced constraints hinder employee creativity. Meanwhile, Dul and Ceylan (2014) found that creativity-supporting environments lead to more successful product introductions.

Risk taking. Entrepreneurship, a driving force for economic growth, inherently involves risk, with higher risk tolerance favoring entrepreneurial pursuits (Chanda & Unel, 2021). Mason et al. (2015) defines risk-taking as bold actions, venturing into the unknown, and committing resources to uncertain ventures. Thus, to enhance the competitive edge, managers must embrace uncertainty and take calculated risks (Hoskisson, 2017). Abdullahi et al. (2019) assert that a competitive aggressive approach positively impacts financial performance, recommending its adoption for performance enhancement. With the perspective on decision-making in uncertain situations, Mousavi and Gigerenzer (2014) emphasized the importance of knowledge and deliberate use of heuristics, suggesting that ignoring some information can lead to more effective outcomes and efficient resource use.

Entrepreneurial Culture. Entrepreneurial culture encompasses the attitudes, values, skills, and risk-taking abilities of individuals and groups within an organization (Danish et al., 2019). Engelen et al. (2014) discovered that adhocratic organizational cultures are highly effective in fostering entrepreneurial orientation. Additionally, employers have the capacity to shape the organizational culture and enhance overall job satisfaction among their employees, as highlighted by the work of Soomro and Shah (2019). Employees may be prompt to seek alternative employment under challenging working conditions but motivated and supported ones stay committed (Yunita & Saputra, 2019). Hence, it is important to prioritize learning-oriented behaviors among leaders and employees to address diversity challenges in dynamic environments (Lui, Zhu & Wang, 2023).

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. Quaranta (2017) stated that a descriptive-correlational research design does not need to establish a causal connection among variables for its main focus to describe and measure their relationship. Descriptive research is a research design that describe a phenomenon and its characteristics. This research is more interested in what rather than how or why something has happened (Nassaji, 2015). On the other hand, correlational research seeks to measure the degree of association between variables (Phyllis, 2014). This research is descriptive for it described the level of intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy of employees on medium-sized companies. The study utilized a correlational research approach since the study sought to establish the relationship between intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy.

Respondents

This study was conducted in Midsayap, Cotabato to examine the impact of intellectual capital to entrepreneurship strategy in the case of medium-sized companies. The study was conducted in this locale due to the emergent of medium-sized companies due to its progressive development. The respondents of this study were the different employees on medium-sized companies. A total of 50 respondents were included in the study using a purposive sampling technique.

Instrument

The study used an adapted questionnaire with minor modification from Sadq et al. (2020) for both intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy. It is composed of three parts. The first part was the demographic profile of the employees on medium-sized companies' respondents in terms of job classification and years of experience. The second part of the questionnaire contains the intellectual capital in terms of structural capital, human capital, and customer capital. The third part of the questionnaire contains the entrepreneurship strategy in terms of creative capabilities, risk taking, and entrepreneurial culture. The Likert scale was used to determine the answers that best align with the view of the respondents in the second part where the indicator lies. Usually, it consists of five options and each question is a statement. The respondent may agree or disagree to the statements with the following scale: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Moderately Agree (3), Disagree (2), Strongly disagree (1). The researchers established a face validity by seeking expert judgement from their teacher, adviser, and validators in modifying the research instrument. Furthermore, it was provided in the original instrument the reliability coefficient of the questionnaire. For the intellectual capital "0.849" and "0.827" for entrepreneurship strategy. This means that the instruments are reliable.

Procedure

To conduct the study, the researchers sought permission from the Dean of the College of Business and Accountancy. They submitted a request letter, signed by the researchers and noted by the research adviser, to the Midsayap Business Permit and Licensing Office (BPLO) to obtain a list of medium-sized enterprises. Upon receiving approval from the Dean and acquiring the list from the BPLO, the researchers sent a request letter to conduct the survey to the identified enterprises. The researchers began distributing the survey questionnaires to the respondents after obtaining consent from the heads of the medium-sized companies. They also addressed any inquiries regarding the administration of the survey. Once all the questionnaires were collected, the data was promptly provided to the

statistician for aggregation and analysis using appropriate statistical methods.

Ethical Considerations

The study used an adapted questionnaire with minor modification from Sadq et al. (2020) for both intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy. The instrument has undergone a minor modification to align with the specific requirements of this research. The researchers established a face validity by seeking expert judgement from their teacher, adviser, and validators in modifying the research instrument. Furthermore, it was provided in the original instrument the reliability coefficient of the questionnaire. Moreover, the privacy of participants' data was rigorously protected during the research phase. The data collection process was conducted meticulously to prevent any privacy violations. Nonetheless, to preserve anonymity, the researchers' refrained from including individual names or company details in the process. This methodology highlights the researcher's dedication to maintain the highest ethical standard in research and honoring the privacy rights of all respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the result and findings of the study. The results are presented in tabular forms.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of Respondent*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Job Classification		
Marketing Department	13	26
HR Department	3	6
IT Department	4	8
Customer Support/Service Representatives	11	22
Finance Department	9	18
Others	8	16
Total	50	100
Years of Experience		
1 to 5 years	25	50
6 to 10 years	9	18
11 to 15 years	5	10
More than 16 years	11	22
Total	50	100

According to the data presented in Table 1, the highest frequency of respondents is observed among those who belong in the Marketing Department, accounting for thirteen (13) out of fifty (50) respondents or twenty-six percent (26%). Conversely, the lowest frequency is observed among those who belong in HR Department, accounting for only one (3) out of fifty (50) respondents or six percent (6%). In terms of years of experience, the majority of the respondents has been serving for 1 to 5 years, comprising twenty-five (25) out of fifty (50) respondents or fifty (50%). On the other hand, only eight (5) out of fifty (50) respondents, or sixteen percent (10%), worked for 11 to 15 years.

Level of Intellectual Capital

Table 2. *Level of Intellectual Capital*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
A. Human Capital	4.14	0.73	Agree	High
B. Structural Capital	4.19	0.78	Agree	High
C. Customer Capital	4.18	0.76	Agree	High
Grand Mean and Average Standard Deviation	4.17	0.76	Agree	High

Table 2 presents the level of intellectual capital in medium-sized companies in terms of human capital, structural capital, and customer capital. The result reveals the highest indicator is structural capital, rated as Agree with a mean of 4.19 and a standard deviation of 0.78. On the other hand, the lowest indicator is human capital, rated as Agree with a mean of 4.14 and a standard deviation of 0.73. Overall, the level of intellectual capital in medium-sized companies is rated as Agree with a grand mean of 4.17 and an average standard deviation of 0.76.

Level of Entrepreneurship Strategy

Table 3 shows the level of entrepreneurship strategy in medium-sized companies in the aspect of creative capabilities, risk taking, and entrepreneurial culture. The finding displays that the highest indicator is entrepreneurial culture with a mean of 4.18 and a standard deviation of 0.77, rated as Agree. Meanwhile, the lowest indicator is creative capabilities with a mean of 4.10 and a standard deviation of 0.75, rated as Agree.

In general, the level of entrepreneurship strategy in medium-sized companies is rated as Agree with a grand mean of 4.13 and an average standard deviation of 0.76.

Table 3. *Level of Entrepreneurship Strategy*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
A. Creative Capabilities	4.10	0.75	Agree	High
B. Risk Taking	4.11	0.76	Agree	High
C. Entrepreneurial Culture	4.18	0.77	Agree	High
Grand Mean and Average Standard Deviation	4.13	0.76	Agree	High

Relationship Between Intellectual Capital and Entrepreneurship Strategy

The table presents a significant relationship between intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy using the Spearman rank correlation. The computed correlation coefficient is equal to 0.942 which implies that a very high correlation exists between intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy. There is sufficient evidence to conclude that there is a significant linear relationship between intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy because the correlation coefficient is significantly different from zero. The p-value of 0.000 is lesser than the level of significance of 0.05, thus, the decision to reject the null hypothesis is made.

Table 4. *Relationship Between Intellectual Capital and Entrepreneurship Strategy*

Variables	N	Df	r-value	p-value	Indication	Decision
Intellectual Capital						Reject the Null Hypothesis
Entrepreneurship Strategy	50	49	0.942	0.000	Significant	

NS – Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on the frequency and percentage distribution, it shows that most of the respondents belong to Marketing Department, accounting for thirteen (13) out of fifty (50) respondents or twenty-six percent (26%). Moreover, most of them has a work experience of 1 to 5 years with twenty-five (25) out of fifty (50) respondents or fifty percent (50%).

The level of intellectual capital in medium-sized companies is evaluated in terms of human capital, structural capital, and customer capital. In terms of human capital, finding reveals that the company has human resources with diverse skills, expertise, and knowledge. This indicates that companies have manpower with good abilities and capacities to perform their job. In the aspect of structural capital, research revealed that the company is keen to have a good reputation through its outstanding scientific product by distinguished human resources. This implies that the company's employees actively contribute innovative ideas, making them more likely to be recognized for their proficiency in product development. In the context of customer capital, results showed that the company tries to keep the parties involved with them by providing the best product. This insinuates that medium-sized companies places importance on fostering positive relationship and engagement with various stakeholders such as customers, suppliers, and employees. Nevertheless, the study demonstrated that the company offers the best possible cooperation with other parties to achieve outstanding service performance. This shared perspective, highlights that the company somehow has the commitment to cooperate for exceptional service performance.

The level of entrepreneurship strategy of medium-sized companies is assessed in terms of creative capabilities, risk-taking, and entrepreneurial culture. In the aspect of creative capabilities, results revealed that the company provides an appropriate environment to support creative work. Essentially, the findings suggest that medium-sized companies have successfully instituted a supportive setting, empowering individuals to articulate their creativity and contribute meaningfully to their work. Furthermore, the company follows an aggressive policy to achieve excellence in competitive companies in terms of risk-taking. This implies that medium-sized companies adopt an aggressive strategy aimed to excel in competitive markets. Moreover, results show that the management of the company encourages its employees to work continuously to accomplish the work efficiently and effectively. The strong agreement among respondents suggests a positive perception of the company's management, indicating that employees feel motivated and supported in maintaining a persistent work ethic to achieve tasks with high levels of efficiency and effectiveness.

The study's findings show a significant and positive relationship between intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy. This relationship implies that as a company enhances their intellectual capital in the aspects of human capital, structural capital, and customer capital, its ability to formulate and execute entrepreneurship strategies also tends to improve.

Conclusions

It is therefore concluded that the level of intellectual capital is high in terms of human capital, structural capital, and customer capital. This highlights that medium-sized companies invest in employee development, foster a learning culture, and recognize the value of their workforce which enables continuous operations, innovation and adaptability. Further, the results of the study emphasize that these companies implement entrepreneurship strategy in the aspects of creative capabilities, risk taking, and entrepreneurial culture. The findings suggest that a strong entrepreneurial approach not only drives growth and competitiveness but also enhances the organization's ability to navigate and succeed in dynamic market environments. Lastly, it was also revealed that there is a significant relationship between intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy. The findings indicate that organizations leveraging high levels of intellectual capital are better positioned to innovate, adapt, and thrive in competitive markets. Therefore, it is essential for organizations to strategically manage and invest in their intellectual assets to drive entrepreneurial success and maintain a competitive edge.

While this study offers valuable insights into the relationship between intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy, it is important to recognize several limitations. Firstly, the relatively small sample size may restrict the generalizability of the findings. Secondly, the reliance on self-reported data could introduce bias and impact the accuracy of the results. However, despite these limitations, the study offers a foundational understanding of how intellectual capital influences entrepreneurship strategy and highlights areas for further investigation.

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